

A SURGICAL CASE OF ECTOPIC RIGHT ATROPHIC TESTIS AS HERNIA - CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Ectopic testis is a developmental anomaly where the testis lies outside the normal path of descent, most commonly in the superficial inguinal pouch. When associated with atrophy, the testis is non-functional and carries an increased risk of malignant transformation. Management of such cases remains controversial, especially in post-pubertal males.

Objective: To outline the rationale, indications, and oncological principles of high inguinal orchidectomy in the management of ectopic atrophic testis.

Clinical findings: A 60 year old male having complaints of swelling in Right inguinal region since many years with mild tenderness but didn't opt for any management. Imaging and clinical features supported the diagnosis of bilateral inguinal hernia. After careful assessment, the overall presentation favoured the diagnosis of bilateral inguinal hernia with right monorchism. Based on surgical principles, this diagnosis for surgical management was made.

Methods: An ectopic atrophic testis is evaluated clinically. High inguinal orchidectomy is performed via an inguinal incision with early high ligation of the spermatic cord at the internal inguinal ring prior to mobilization of the testis. The specimen is subjected to histopathological examination.

Results: High orchidectomy ensures complete removal of the testis along with its lymphatic drainage, which follows the testicular vessels to para-aortic nodes. This approach minimizes tumour spillage, avoids violation of scrotal lymphatics, and allows accurate pathological staging. Atrophic testes, despite being small and non-functional, have a 4–8 fold increased risk of germ cell neoplasia, with intratubular germ cell neoplasia or seminoma found in 5–10% of cases. In post-pubertal patients, orchidectomy eliminates malignancy risk, chronic pain, and recurrent torsion, with minimal morbidity.

Conclusion: High inguinal orchidectomy is the procedure of choice for ectopic atrophic testis in adults due to the significant malignant potential of dysgenetic testicular tissue. Adherence to oncological principles with high ligation at the internal ring is mandatory even in atrophic testes. In pre-pubertal children with viable ectopic testis, orchiopexy may be considered, but orchidectomy is preferred when the testis is severely atrophic. Preoperative counselling regarding hypogonadism and fertility is essential.

Keywords: Ectopic testis, Testicular atrophy, High orchidectomy, monorchism, Testicular malignancy

Testicular Atrophy

INTRODUCTION :

The descent of the testis from the intra-abdominal location to the scrotum is a complex developmental process regulated by hormonal and mechanical factors. Any deviation from the normal path results in mal-adescent. Cryptorchidism is the broader term for undescended testis, which affects 1–4% of full-term male neonates and up to 30% of premature infants. Among the forms of mal-adescent, ectopic testis is a rare entity, accounting for 5–10% of all undescended testes. In ectopic testis, the testis deviates from the normal line of descent after passing through the external inguinal ring and comes to lie in an abnormal anatomical position. Common sites include the superficial inguinal pouch (Denis Browne pouch), femoral region, pubic, perineal, penile, and contralateral scrotum. This is distinct from an undescended testis, which arrests along the normal pathway. Prolonged malposition of the testis exposes it to higher temperatures, abnormal pressure, and poor vascularity, leading to progressive histological changes. Over time, the testis undergoes atrophy, characterized by reduction in volume <math><3-4\text{ ml}</math> in adults, loss of germ cells, Sertoli cell-only pattern, interstitial fibrosis and impaired Leydig cell function. An atrophic testis is clinically soft, small, and non-tender. The clinical significance of an ectopic atrophic testis lies in three major concerns:

1. **Infertility:** Atrophic testes are non-functional with absent spermatogenesis and diminished testosterone production.
2. **Malignancy:** Testicular mal-adescent is the strongest risk factor for germ cell tumours. Ectopic atrophic testes have a 4–8 fold increased risk of malignancy compared to normally descended testes. The risk persists even after orchiopexy if performed late, due to intrinsic dysgenesis.
3. **Torsion & Trauma:** Abnormal mobility and fixation predispose to acute torsion. The superficial location also makes it vulnerable to injury. While orchiopexy is preferred for viable ectopic testis in children, the management of an ectopic atrophic testis, especially in post-pubertal males, often necessitates orchidectomy. The choice of surgical approach becomes critical due to the malignant potential of dysgenetic testicular tissue. High inguinal orchidectomy, with ligation of the spermatic cord at the internal inguinal ring, follows oncological principles and remains the standard of care.

2. CASE REPORT : A 60 year old diabetic male patient, a farmer by profession presented with complaints of swelling at right inguinal region since 7-8 years noticed and having slight tenderness in the same region since 3-4 years. There were no complaints of acute abdomen or severe pain. In view of the progression of symptoms and non-resolving nature of the condition despite multiple options of management, the patient sought treatment at the OPD and was admitted for further evaluation and management. The patient had H/O tuberculosis (TB) pulmonary 30 years ago and had been on regular evaluation and medication for the same as prescribed by his physician for 6 consecutive months. There was no history of any major chronic illness. There was a past surgical history of operate for Left eye cataract , which was performed at another hospital 1 year ago. The patient belongs to a low socioeconomic background. He gives a history of chronic nicotine consumption for the past 10 years, with a consumption of approximately 1 packet per day. On examination, the patient was conscious and oriented to time, place and person. Physical examination revealed no signs of pallor, cyanosis, clubbing, Lymphadenopathy, oedema and vitals were stable. Systemic examination did not reveal any abnormalities. Clinical findings The patient presented with swelling at Right inguinal inguinal region since 7-8 years with mild intermittent pain in the same region since 2-3 years. The patient got admitted for surgical management for the above complaints.

GENERAL EXAMINATION

TABLE 1: General Examination

Sr no.	Parameter	Findings
1	Pulse	74/min
2	Blood Pressure	110/70mmHg
3	SpO ₂	98% at room air
4.	Temperature	98.2 ⁰ F
5.	Aakruti	Madhyam
6.	Twak Varna	Shyava
7.	Jivha	Niraam
8.	Shabd	Spastha
9.	Sparsha	Samshitoshna
10.	Druka	Spastha
11.	Mala	Samyaka
12.	Mutra	Samyaka
13.	CVS	S ₁ S ₂ normal
14.	RS	AE=BE
15.	Abdomen	Soft, non-tender
16.	Liver	Not palpable
17.	Spleen	Not palpable

LOCAL EXAMINATION(STHANIK PARIKSHAN)**Inguino-scrotal region**

- Swelling at Right inguinal region - reducible in nature .
- Localized temperature - not raised.
- Cough impulse test - positive
- Finger invagination test - felt at tip of finger.
- Right testis was not palpable.

AYURVEDIC ASSESMENT

Table 2: Ayurvedic Assesment of Patient

Parameter	Findings
Dosha	Vata, Pitta , Kapha
Dushya	Rasa , Rakta, Mamsa
Srotas involved	Mansavaha, Medovaha

INVESTIGATIONS**CBC(17/5/2026)**

Table 3: CBC Findings on (17/05/2026)

Investigation	Result
Haemoglobin	14.5 g/dl
RBC	4.5 million/mm ³
TLC	7,700 cells/mm ³
Platelet count	3,81,000/mm ³

Liver Function Test (17/05/2026)

Table 4: LFT Findings on (17/05/2026)

Sr.	Investigation	Result
1.	Sr Bilirubin Total	0.92 mg/dl
2.	SGOT	38 IU/L
3.	SGPT	20 IU/L

Kidney Function Test (17/05/2026)

Table 5: KFT Findings on (17/05/2026)

Sr.	Investigations	Result
1.	Sr. Creatinine	1.10 mg/dl
2.	Sr. Urea	18.56 mg/dl
3.	Sr. Na ⁺	135 mmol/L
4.	Sr. K ⁺	4 mmol/L

SEROLOGY (17/05/2026)

Table 6: SEROLOGY on (17/05/2026)

Sr.	Investigations	Result
1.	HIV I & II	Non reactive
2.	HbsAg	Negative

Urine (R/M) (17/5/2026)

Table 7: Urine (R/M) on (17/05/2026)

Sr.	Investigations	Result
1.	Protein	+ve
2.	Glucose	Nil
3.	Pus cells	1-2/HPF
4.	Epithelial cells	6-8/HPF

OTHER INVESTIGATIONS

ECG- Normal Sinus Rhythm

Xray Chest PA view - Normal

USG abdomen & pelvis-(18/5/2026)

S/O bilateral inguinal hernia with herniation of mesentery right side measuring a defect of size approximately 1.74 cm and Lt side of about 0.82 cm. Right testis was not seen.

USG - ABDOMEN

USG - SCROTUM

USG FILM

तारीख	प्रतिदिन के रक्तचाप	समाप्ति विकिस्ता (एचएम)	जोषी (समन) विकिस्ता	पथ
20/05/26 9:30am		अंडाराय निर्दोष अंगुली (Orchidectomy consent)	पत्रक	
	मी, ५		60 years old Male.	
	हया महिनोरया	आंडार समजणे	आहे की. मांड्या	
	अजया बाजुयया	Inguinal Hernia	शस्त्रक्रिये	
	असमान, साआ	अजवा अंडकोष	[RHS]	
	अनपेक्षितपणे	आढळया आहे.		
	आकरावली	मना सांगिल्ले	की. त्याला शस्त्रक्रिये -	
	दवारा काढणे (Orchidectomy)	आवश्यक आहे		
	मी समजुन	हीतले आहे.		
	1) शस्त्रक्रियेन	अंडकोष काढणे	जखणे आहे	
	2) आमुळे रिडे	शकणजे फायदे	जाणि संभाव्य प्रोब्लेम्स	
	(होमोन उत्पादन)	प्रजनन शक्ती	, इतर शस्त्रक्रियेच्या	
	प्रोब्लेम्स) मया	स्पष्ट करव्यात	आव्या आहेत	
	3) पेट्याची	अपघाराबाबत मया	माहिती देण्यात आली	
	आहे			
	4) मी मांड्या	संश्लेषित शस्त्रक्रिया	पुढे भेटुन	
	करव्यात	तयार आहे.		

ORCHIDECTOMY CONSENT

PAKWAS SAMANVAY RUGNALAY, HANUMAN NAGAR NAGPUR
SHALYA TANTRA DEPARTMENT
OT CONSENT

DATE 19/5/26

Sex Male Age 60 years

IPD number C-39, 1025 Pakwasa Samanvay Rugnalay, Nagpur.

Hereby giving my consent for the Surgery/Treatment/Investigation / Anaesthesia as follows.

I am having Right Inguinal Hernia for which Right Inguinal Hernioplasty surgery is needed. Risk and ill effects, if surgery is not done are well explained to me by Dr. Dr. Shank Madam, Dr. Naitikale Sir

- I have been explained other methods of surgeries for my disease, amongs them I/we (relatives) choose the above mentioned one.
- I have been informed that, None of the surgical procedures are 100% safe. Any treatment / investigation / anaesthesia or surgery could be life threatening occasionally for healthy individuals also.
- Complications like Excessive hemorrhage, infection, cardiac arrest, pulmonary embolism and many other sudden unknown complications may arise during surgery or anaesthesia. Patient may have to be shifted to other hospitals / ICU in case of emergency. Doctors have explained this to us and we are ready for it at our expenses.
- During operation, due to some reasons, if doctors have to change the modality or type of surgery, or in must situations if they have to remove an organ / part of the body, I will be agree with this change and give my consent for the same.
- After operation instead of getting benefit I may get some other problems like e.g. bleeding/infection/pain at operated site, recurrence of the disease, infection / inflammation to neighbouring structures of operated site etc. We will take good care of it and will be agree to take another treatment for same as advised by doctor.
- I give permission and consent to treating doctors or authorized persons of the hospital to examine and then dispose off the excised / removed parts of my body during surgery.
- I give consent to take and publish photos / videos of surgery for enrichment of medical knowledge and research work. I consider my identity will be kept secret in it.
- All my/our doubts and questions have been answered and I/we are satisfied. My consent can be confirmed from all above information.
- Doctors have given me/ us the approximate estimate of Rs. _____ for operative expenditure. In case of some complications during surgery, expenditure of OT & Hospital may increase. Investigation & Hospital charges and medical charges are different than said above estimate. I/we will pay all hospital bills and other expenses before discharge. I have been explained all above written matter. I understood it and hence give my full consent for it. Blank spaces have been filled and unnecessary points have been scratched before signing the document.

Date 19/5/26 Time 11 AM

Name of Doctor Dr. Shank Madam Name and sign of patient _____

Sign of Doctor [Signature] Name and sign of relative _____

Relation with patient _____

OPERATIVE CONSENT

Pakwasa Samanvay Rughalaya
Hanuman Nagar, Nagpur
Shalya Tantra Department

OPERATION NO.

Name of Patient: [Redacted]
Date: 20/12/26 Time Start: 8 AM Finish: 11:20 AM
Diagnosis: Right inguinal hernia & (R) ectopic atrophic undescended testis & rudimentary spermatic cord as content & (L) direct inguinal hernia & (L) undescended testis & rudimentary spermatic cord as content.
Surgeon: Dr. Dr. Shinde Ma'am
Dr. Dr. Naikwade sir
Assistant Surgeon: Dr. Vaishnavi, Dr. Bishabh, Dr. Pranav
Anaesthesia: Spinal & epidural anaesthesia
Anaesthetist: Dr. Dr. Nagarkar sir

Operative Procedure: Right high level orchiopexy & Bassinis repair & meshplasty & Left inguinal hernioplasty & Bassinis repair & meshplasty & LIS & scrotoscopy & SA & epidural
Findings: - Right ectopic & atrophic testis & rudimentary spermatic cord as hernial content.

- Left direct inguinal hernia
- Interoexternal haemorrhoids at 3:6, 7 & 11 o'clock position.
- Surgery Notes:
 - L.AAP & SA & Epidural anaesthesia, patient in supine position, parts painted, draped & isolated.
 - Incision taken on skin at 1.25 cm above & parallel to midinguinal point.
 - Camper's fascia incised & line of incision.
 - superficial external pudendal & superficial external epigastric vessels identified & cauterised.
 - Scarpa's fascia incised.
 - External oblique aponeurosis identified & incised.
 - Incision extended upto superficial ring medially & upto deep ring laterally.
 - Iliinguinal nerve identified & separated from cord
- Specimen Sent for HPE: YES/NO
by blunt dissection.
- spermatic cord identified.

- The hernial sac was identified & opened.
- Right ectopic & atrophic testis along & rudimentary spermatic cord found as a content of hernial sac in inguinal canal.
- Adhesions around the sac & cord structures carefully dissected & released.
- The rudimentary spermatic cord separated upto the level of deep inguinal ring.
- The cord structures clamped, transfixed, ligated & help of cautery along & testis.
- High level right orchiectomy done.
- lower margins of conjoint tendon & inner margin of inguinal ligament sutured & prolene 1-0 & simple interrupted sutures. Bassinis repair done.
- Polypropylene mesh placed & fixed & 1st stitch taken over peritoneum of Rt pubic tubercle & transfixed & prolene 1-0 & mesh fixed & inguinal ligament inferiorly & conjoint tendon superiorly & prolene 1-0. Haemostasis achieved.
- Inj Amikacin sooty sprinkled over the mesh. meshplasty done.
- External oblique closure done & continuous interlocking sutures & prolene 2-0.
- Fatty layer closed & vicryl 2-0 & sily buried interrupted suture.
- Skin closure done & stapler suture.
- Betadine soaked gauze kept over suture line.
- Packed well.
- Dressing done.

Signature
BAMS
P.T.O

Pakwasa Samanvay Rughalaya
Hanuman Nagar, Nagpur
Shalya Tantra Department

OPERATION NOTES

Name of Patient: [Redacted]
Date: 20/12/26 Time Start: 8 AM Finish: 11:20 AM
Diagnosis: (R) inguinal hernia & (R) ectopic atrophic undescended testis & rudimentary spermatic cord as content & (L) direct inguinal hernia & (L) undescended testis & rudimentary spermatic cord as content.
Surgeon: Dr. Dr. Shinde Ma'am
Dr. Dr. Naikwade Sir
Assistant Surgeon: Dr. Vaishnavi, Dr. Bishabh, Dr. Pranav
Anaesthesia: Spinal & Epidural Anaesthesia
Anaesthetist: Dr. Dr. Nagarkar Sir

Operative Procedure: (R) High level orchiopexy & Bassinis repair & meshplasty & (L) inguinal hernioplasty & Bassinis repair & meshplasty & LIS & scrotoscopy & SA & epidural
Findings: - Right ectopic & atrophic testis & rudimentary spermatic cord as hernial content.

- Surgery Notes: - L.AAP & SA patient in supine position, parts painted, draped & isolated.
- An incision taken on (R) side skin 1.25 cm above & parallel to midline 2/3rd of inguinal ligament.
- Camper's fascia incised along & line of incision.
- superficial epigastric & external pudendal vessels identified & cauterised.
- Scarpa's fascia incised along, cross cross fibre i.e. external oblique aponeurosis identified, 1cm incision taken.
- Incision extended upto superficial inguinal ring medially & deep inguinal ring laterally.
- Iliinguinal nerve, spermatic cord & cord lipoma identified.
- Distal component of Nerve seen behind spermatic cord.
- Lateralization of cord done by securing it laterally to external oblique flap.
- Specimen Sent for HPE: YES/NO
Signature
- Inner border of inguinal ligament & lower border of conjoint tendon sutured & prolene 1-0 for strengthening the posterior wall
- Bassinis repair done

- Polypropylene mesh placed & fixed & 1st stitch taken over peritoneum of (R) pubic tubercle & fixed & prolene 1-0 & mesh fixed & inguinal ligament inferiorly & conjoint tendon superiorly & prolene 1-0
- Inj Amikacin sooty sprinkled over mesh.
- Spermatic cord kept in anatomical position.
- External oblique aponeurosis closed & prolene 2-0 & continuous interlocking sutures
- Haemostasis achieved
- Fatty layer closed & vicryl 2-0 & subcutaneous suture.
- Skin closure done & stapler suture.
- Suture line cleaned & betadine solution soaked gauze.
- Betadine soaked gauze kept over suture line.
- Packed well.

Foley's catheterization Notes

- L.AAP patient in supine position, penile region and its periphery cleaned & betadine soap.
- Lot 2-1 jelly applied over urethral Meatus and on tip of catheter.
- No Foley's catheter gently inserted in urethral Meatus upto its full length.
- 15 ml urine collected in bncac.
- Probub inflated & 15 ml distilled water.
- Foley's catheterization done.

Signature
BAMS
P.T.O

OPERATIVE NOTES FOR RIGHT SIDE HIGH ORCHIDECTOMY WITH BASSINIS REPAIR WITH MESHPLASTY WITH LEFT INGUINAL HERNIOPLASTY WITH BASSINIS REPAIR

Operative procedure:

Table 8: Operative Details

Parameter	Details
Date	19/05/2026
Time	9:00 am
Anaesthesia	Spinal Anaesthesia with Epidural
Procedure	Right side high Orchidectomy with Bassini repair with Meshplasty with Left Inguinal Hernioplasty with Bassini repair

Preoperative profile-

- Informed and written consent taken
- Notification to operation theatre Staff was done.
- Physician fitness taken.
- Parts Preparation was done.
- Soft Diet since evening was advised
- Scrubbing with Betadine and Savlon was done
- Patient was kept Nil by mouth since Midnight
- Proctoclysis Enema was given to patient.
- Inj. T.T 0.5ml IM given stat
- Inj. Bupivacaine sensitivity test done
- Inj. Ceftriaxone + Sulbactam 1.5 gm IV in 100 ml NS given
- Inj. Pantaprazole 40 mg IV given stat
- IV Fluid DNS 500ml given stat

OPERATIVE PROCEDURE:

- Under AAP with Epidural anaesthesia patient in supine position, Parts painted, draped & isolated
- Incision taken on skin at 1.25 cm above & parallel to mid inguinal point.
- Camper's fascia incised & line of incision, Scarpa's fascia incised, External oblique aponeurosis identified & incised.
- Incision extended upto superficial ring medially & upto deep ring laterally.
- Ilioinguinal nerve identified & separated from cord by blunt dissection.
- Spermatic cord along with the hernial sac was identified & opened.
- Right ectopic & atrophic testis along & rudimentary spermatic cord found as a content of hernial sac in inguinal canal.
- Adhesions around the same a cord structures carefully dissected and released.
- The rudimentary spermatic cord separated upto the level of deep inguinal ring.
- The cord structures clamped transfixed, ligated with vicryl 2-0 at the base of deep inguinal ring. & excised out with thr help of cautery along with testis.
- Excision of spermatic cord along with High level right orchidectomy done.
- Bassini's repair done, Polypropylene Meshplasty done , Inj. amikacin 500mg sprinkled over the mesh.
- Haemostasis achieved and checked. Wound closure done in layers.

- Left inguinal hernioplasty with bassinis repair done for left indirect inguinal hernia.

Post operative care:

Table 9: medicine and dosage

Medicine	Dose
IV Fluid NS/RL/DNS	@ 80 ML/HR
Inj. Ceftriaxone + Sulbactam	1.5gm IV in 100 ml NS
Inj. Amikacin	500 mg IV BD
Inj. Pantaprazole	40 mg IV OD
Inj. Tramadol hydrochloride	100 mg in 100 ml NS

INSTRUCTIONS

- Nil by mouth till good peristalsis confirmed.
- Epidural infiltration 12 hourly.
- Monitoring I/O charting

SAMPLE OF ATROPHIC TESTIS WITH RUDIMENTARY CORD EXCISED OUT

POD-1

POD-14

DISCUSSION

An ectopic right atrophic testis presenting within or as a hernial sac is a surgical trap. It looks like a routine inguinal hernia but carries high malignancy risk. USG Doppler pre-operative are essential. Intra-operative identification of atrophic testis mandates conversion to high inguinal orchidectomy rather than simple herniotomy. This adheres to oncological principles and prevents future morbidity.

Differential Diagnosis:

1. Funicular hernia with lipoma of cord – lipoma feels softer
2. Encysted hydrocele of cord – transilluminant, no impulse
3. Lymph node in inguinal hernia – firm but separate from cord
4. Femoral hernia – below inguinal ligament

Special Scenarios:

1. Child <2 yrs with ectopic viable testis: Orchiopexy + herniotomy preferred. Biopsy if dysgenetic.
2. Adult >32 yrs: Orchidectomy mandatory. Orchiopexy doesn't reduce cancer risk. Bilateral case: Check testosterone. If sole testis, counsel for lifelong HRT before orchidectomy
3. Incidental finding on table: Convert hernia repair to high orchidectomy. Take consent for orchidectomy pre-op if suspected.

Clinical pearl: “Empty scrotum + inguinal hernia = Think ectopic testis until proven otherwise.”

CONCLUSION : The undescended ectopic Right atrophic testis clinically found as a indirect inguinal hernial content which was planned for Right inguinal hernioplasty with Bassini repair was incidentally found on operating table got decided and underwent the surgical intervention of high orchidectomy with Bassini repair with Meshplasty . Patient and his relatives were counselled well about the effects and circumstances in removing the atrophic testis of the patient and after having orchidectomy consent from the patients relatives this procedure was conducted uneventfully. Patient was advised to have an abdominal binder along with scrotal support for 3 months for supporting the mesh from outside and is counselled to avoid his addiction on intoxications and routines that might lead the patients abdominal pressure to hamper.

Declaration of Patient Consent – The authors confirm that they have acquired a patient consent form, in which the patient or caregiver has granted permission for the publication of the case, including accompanying images and other clinical details, in the journal. The patient or caregiver acknowledges that their name and initials will not be disclosed, and sincere attempts will be undertaken to safeguard their identity. However, complete anonymity cannot be assured.

Patient’s Perspective: I was advised to remove my right testis which was not functional. I was worried because without my one testis will there be any health effects . I visited this hospital where the treatment was done nicely . I can resumed my routine work within one month. The condition will not recur anymore. During the treatment, doctor advised me to stop tobacco and smoking and following this advice, I was able to quit smoking. I was told to wear abdominal belt for 3 months interval.

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